

Challenges of Virtual Validation and Verification for Automotive Functions - Supplementary Materials

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1 Survey questions

To gain deeper insights into the challenges encountered in the course of the EVIDENT project [2], we sent out a survey, as discussed in the main paper [1], that included Likert and open-ended questions about the nature of the challenges, their possible solutions, and potential roadblocks.

For each of the challenges, we provided a description based on the discussions and we asked whether the challenge was encountered by the respondent:

- (a) In the scope of the EVIDENT project.
- (b) In the scope of the EVIDENT project and other similar projects.
- (c) Never, but they had some experience or comments on it.
- (d) Never.

If the respondent responded anything except never having experienced the challenge nor having comments on the solution, a new set of questions were presented to them:

1. Can you tell us more about the challenge?
2. What was the degree of agreement among the participants regarding the challenge and the best way to address it?
 - Answered with a Likert scale from 1 (Low agreement on how to address the challenge) to 5 (High agreement on how to address the challenge).
3. What solutions were proposed for addressing the challenge?
4. What do you think is the degree of certainty about what results will be generated from the solutions proposed for addressing the challenge?
 - Answered with a Likert scale from 1 (Low certainty about success/appropriateness of proposed solutions) to 5 (High certainty about success/appropriateness of proposed solutions).
5. What roadblocks are there to achieve this solution?

After responding these questions for those challenges they had experienced during EVIDENT or other projects, or that they had comments on, all respondents were asked to classify each of the challenges into:

- (a) Already solved
- (b) Next frontier
- (c) Long-term future

Finally, all respondents were asked the open-ended question “Would you like to add challenges that you faced during EVIDENT and were not covered here?”

The responses were automatically gathered and tabulated by Microsoft Forms.

2 Agreement-certainty matrix

In the final step of the workshop, described in the main paper [1], we asked the participants to categorize the challenges based on two dimensions: the degree of agreement among the project partners regarding the way to address the challenge; and the degree of certainty on whether results will be generated from it. This activity was done in two groups followed by a joint discussion. As a result, challenges were categorized according to an Agreement-Certainty Matrix [3].

Figures 1 and 2 show how the challenges were categorized by the two groups of workshop participants. These classifications as well as the posterior discussion of the differences between the groups were used to further refine and classify the challenges described in the main paper [1].

Fig. 1. Agreement on and certainty about how to address the challenges: final classification of identified challenges by group 1.

Fig. 2. Agreement on and certainty about how to address the challenges: final classification of identified challenges by group 2.

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References

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